

Description of scurvy by Vander Mye (1624)

Summary by James Lind (1772)

Vander Mye described the occurrence of scurvy epidemic in the siege of Breda. This is James Lind's English summary (1772), the original is in Latin.

Siege of Breda

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/siege_of_Breda_\(1624\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/siege_of_Breda_(1624))

[https://www.wikiwand.com/en/siege_of_Breda_\(1624\)](https://www.wikiwand.com/en/siege_of_Breda_(1624))

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Breda>

"After a ten-month siege in 1624–25, the city again surrendered to the Spaniards, now led by Spinola; the event was immortalized by Diego Velázquez."

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Timeline_of_Breda

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections.

This text is available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225429>

This annotated version was prepared by:

Harri Hemilä, University of Helsinki, Finland

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

Lind J 1772

p.535

In the course of my experiments on patients in the scurvy, I have relieved some in such circumstances, by the most trifling prescriptions; and am persuaded, that entire credit may be given to the relation of cures similar to this published by **Vander Mye** and other authors of unquestionable veracity.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/534/mode/2up>

Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment. *Nutr Rev.* 2009 Jun;67(6):315-32.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.2009.00205.x>

p.319

The surgeons or surgeons' mates of the world's navies and armies seem to have had no difficulty in learning to diagnose scurvy from its typical clear-cut features, well described in their standard texts. It is remarkable in the many descriptions of privations, both at land and sea, characteristic specific clinical features are recognizable today as those of scurvy, and only rarely of other diseases such as those caused by deficiencies of other vitamins (A, B, etc). Indeed, Lind cited the statements of other highly experienced clinicians... **Vander Mye** at Breda stated: "The scurvy is not a hodge-podge or complication of various different diseases, but is itself a simple identical malady." Moreover, most of those diagnosed then with scurvy responded rapidly, within hours or days,⁶⁷ when given what we now know to be effective antiscorbutics, unlike the slower responses to treatments of other known avitaminoses.

The text below is from Lind (1772; 3rd ed) p.343-355.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/342/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/342/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=367>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=365>

Original version in Latin:

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5327135542&seq=3>

<https://books.google.fi/books?hl=fi&lr=&id=PS5kAAAACAAJ>

https://books.google.fi/books/about/Frederici_vander_Mye_De_morbis_et_sympto.html?id=ESJgAAAACAAJ

1627

Frederic Vander Mye, de morbis et symptomatibus popularibus Bredanis, tempore obsidionis, et eorum immutationibus pro anni victusque diversitate, &c. tractatus duo.

p.343

How far the passions and dispositions of the mind contribute to the production and cure of diseases, and how much their symptoms and appearances are diversified by different seasons and by different food, no where more clearly appeared than in the siege of *Breda*. We here saw the progress of the plague, scurvy, and such like diseases, encreased upon the report spread of bad news, but in a manner altogether checked by the arrival of joyful tidings. We here beheld some apparently relieved, many perfectly cured, by their faith in imaginary remedies. Grief and fear greatly injure the human body, and in a particular man-

p.344

ner give strength and vigour to the plague and scurvy.

But we proceed to relate the order in which these diseases occurred, and the influence of the various causes which gave rise and diversity to their appearances. The preceding summer being very warm and dry, produced inflammatory fevers, pains of the side and breast, and sore-throats of a mild nature. Soon after this the plague was brought hither by infection from *Holland*. In the autumn the weather was cloudy and rainy, with southerly winds; the winter also proved wet and open, the season being windy though mild. Here the author very minutely describes the influence of such a state of weather, concurring with the various incidents of joy and grief, hope and despair, in diversifying the symptoms of that dreadful calamity, and in encreasing

or abating the mortality of it. But as such remarks are foreign to our purpose, we shall only observe, that in the end of winter a frost came on, and put an entire stop to the plague. An universal joy now prevailed, occasioned by the daily arrival of messengers encouraging the besieged with the hopes of a speedy relief, and by their own army being already in fight. But these hopes were soon baffled, the attempts of the *Dutch* army proving fruitless. Scarcity of provisions encreasing in the town, and as the frost went off the moist and unwholesome vapours

p.345

from the lakes, added to a damp cloudy rainy *equinox*, produced a new calamity.

The appearance of livid spots on the body, occasioned at first a general consternation. The surgeons who were ignorant, declared the plague to have broken out again; but upon a closer examination, it was found to be the scurvy. This disease seemed to absorb all others; so that for six weeks there was no talk of any other distemper in the town. The calamity became great and universal; few escaped it; many deprived of all-motion, wasting away by piece-meal, toothless and starved, as not being able to chew their food, died in a most piteous condition.

The scurvy proceeded from grief and disappointment, as also from unwholesome food. The States of *Holland* had taken care to provide this city for a siege, with rye, cheese, and dried fish. The cheese and fish had at times been renewed, but their stock of rye had been in store for thirty years, and was become quite spoiled and musty. Being altogether improper for baking, it was mixed up with other grain, and all who eat of it soon began to be attacked with the scurvy. Eating of the old cheese, which was rotten, as also of dogs and horse-flesh, but particularly the wetness of the season, contributed much to the

production of the distemper: the air which the soldiers breathed, and the houses where

p.346

they lay, being extremely damp. They also lay together, so received it by infection; for the disease proves infectious when persons use the same improper food, and breathe the same impure air.

In some the gums were rotten; in others spots only appeared on the body, especially, in such as had discharges of blood, which sometimes prevented, at other times diminished the swelling of the gums. The spots were chiefly upon the legs. They were also to be seen upon the back, arms, breast, neck, as likewise upon the face, even when the gums continued sound; chiefly in such as took care to preserve their teeth, and were continually washing their mouth with astringent compositions of salt, alum, and the like. At first the spots were red, then became purple, afterwards livid, and last of all quite black. The livid spots were very dangerous, but the black still more malignant and fatal. A few of the eruptions put on the appearance of a *St. Anthony's Fire*, and the *cuticle* afterwards fell off in scales. In most patients the skin was of a purple hue. An enervated, heavy and languid body, without having any complaint of real sickness, and a fœtid breath, were symptoms common to all. The knees became afflicted with violent pains at times.

The tendons of the posterior muscles of

p.347

the thigh turned as rigid and hard as a piece of wood, so that the leg being bent altogether back to the buttock, it became quite immovable; and of the joint in the knee, there remained no vestige. Exquisite pains were felt along the course of the *sciatic* nerve, and in the deep-seated joint of the thigh bone. Some expired suddenly and unexpectedly when at their meals; especially

those who had been troubled with palpitations of the heart. The heart itself is greatly affected in the scurvy with palpitations, tremors, frequent stoppage of its motion, a frequent and great oppression, and a defect of natural heat; hence a redundancy of watery and excrementitious humours in the whole body passing off by profuse spitting, urine, and fœtid sweats.

In many the gums grew up to such a pitch as to bury the whole teeth, and sometimes part of the cheek bone dropped off. In this case the misery was intolerable, though the pains gave some little relief by short intermissions; the gangrenous flesh of the gums not having been speedily removed; the taint had spread and preyed upon the bone. The disease was seldom accompanied with a fever, but frequently with a flux. Where there was a fever, it was generally slow and irregular. We observed one or two of these fevers somewhat to resemble the plague. The mouth was dry, though the patient had but

p.348

little inclination to drink; the pulse was small and irregular; there were frequent retchings and at times an unspeakable uneasiness in the breast; hard, black, crusty abscesses appeared on the legs, the anguish of which occasioned often a pain, seldom a tumour in the groin. But fevers at this time were very uncommon.

Of those who were afflicted with the flux, few escaped, and that with great difficulty.

They afterwards became bloated, relaxed and dropsical.¹ Watery swellings of the testicles were frequent. The unhappy patients took a dislike to drugs, and were apparently injured by the operation of violent purges. Some died early in the disease, viz. those who had seldom any evacuation of blood by the nose or stool and seemed from the beginning indolent, dispirited, and blown up as it were with wind. Their stools were greasy, fœtid, and of various colours, but not frequent. The blood drawn from the veins appeared livid, was fœtid and thick, but did not coagulate. The discharges by stool in this disease were indeed commonly watery and greasy, but a flux did not relieve the disease. When there were acute pains of the belly, intestines, and stomach, in this case little hopes of life remained, by reason of the intenseness of the pains, the strength of the patient having been exhausted by the violence of the di-

p.349

stemper. In a word, whether the disease was protracted to a longer or shorten period, most died with an inward indisposition in the belly; the flux proving rather a distinguishing sign of the scurvy than a critical and salutary discharge.

It was observed before, that the scurvy broke out about the equinox, and it quickly increased to an almost incredible degree. On the 20th of *March*, 1625, an account was taken of the number of patients, and there were found 1608 soldiers labouring under it. The sick were ordered to be classed into

three divisions; for the superintendance of each of which a physician, an apothecary, and two surgeons were appointed. Three hours were employed every day in visiting and prescribing for the patients. We here beheld an exact picture of the disease, and at first, even during a time of scarcity, were fortunate enough in its cure. At this period fluxes were so trifling and uncommon, that we gave no attention to them, directing our whole care to remove the disease itself.²

p.350

The number of the afflicted began afterwards daily to decrease, owing partly to the lucky circumstance of our spies having brought into the town a quantity of tobacco, by the use of which many were preserved from the disease, while others were recovered: to this likewise the more liberal use of wine, permitted at this time to be publicly sold, was supposed to have contributed its share: now also the days began to lengthen, the sun to shine forth with comforting heat, and the nights grew warmer; so that in less than a month's time we found the number of scorbutic patients reduced to 800. But these were left in a most pitiful condition indeed! the shops were now exhausted of medicines; the ordinary remedies administered did not avail; our provisions grew daily worse, and so scarce, that the corrupted grain, which by order of the magistrates had been formerly condemned was now ordered to be distributed to the soldiers, and to complete our misfortunes, no appearance presented itself of relief, all

1 Dropsy.

The historical diagnosis of dropsy – which is now obsolete – indicated simply an abnormal accumulation of fluid. The word derives from the Greek *hydrops* (water). Alternative or supplementary terms included *hydrothorax* (fluid in the chest cavity), *ascites* (which still indicates excess free fluid in the abdominal cavity), *anasarca* (still used to describe generalized edema throughout the body).

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521332866.101>

An ancient medical term used to indicate different conditions including chronic heart failure.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2017.07.104>

Scurvy can cause heart failure, eg.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-024-02941-x> <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10949735>

2 In the beginning, the shops being well provided with medicines, this decoction was usually prescribed... The following liniment was directed for the gums...

expectation from the *Dutch* army was gone: *una salus victis nullam sperare salutem.*

We were at this time quite at a loss what measures to pursue: however we put on
p.351

the best countenance³. We changed the medicines, extolled the efficacy of our prescriptions, doubled their dose, talked largely of the number cured, magnifying in every respect our skill and success. By these means we protracted time for near a month longer. But the miserably afflicted began to discover the deceit, particularly such of them as had been before shut up in besieged places, and had observed the like artifices practised. The soldiers, no longer able to suffer in a situation harder to be borne than human nature is accustomed to, gave themselves up entirely to despair. They refused to do any longer duty, delivered up their arms to the Governor, and threatening a mutiny, conspired to surrender the city to the enemy. This the terriblest circumstance of all, viz. their absolute despair, gave rise to a variety of misery; hence proceeded fluxes, dropsies, and every species of distress⁴, attended with a great mortality.

Quis tibi nunc civis cernenti talia sensus.

The physicians at this time giving up entirely with the cure of the disease, direct their whole art to remove the flux, and alleviate the more pressing symptoms. Nothing was left unattempted to recal the drooping spirits of the soldiers, and to allay
p.352

their turbulent minds. Recourse was had even to opium, itself. By such means a truce was gained, but of short duration; for the evacuations being thereby stopped, the legs became more unwieldy. A dropsy ensued, the tendons became rigid,

and sudden death stepped quickly in to put an end to farther woe.

On the 2d of *May*, 1625, when the Prince of *Orange* heard of their distress and understood that the city was in danger of being delivered up to the enemy by the soldiers, he wrote letters addressed to the men, promising them the most speedy relief. These were accompanied with medicines against the scurvy, said to be of great price, but still of greater efficacy: many more were yet to be sent. The effects of this deceit were truly astonishing! three small phials of medicine were given to each physician, not enough for the recovery of two patients. It was publicly given out, that three or four drops were sufficient to impart a healing virtue to a gallon of liquor. We now displayed our wonder-working balsams. Nor were even the commanders let into the secret of the cheat put upon the soldiers. They flocked in crowds about us, every one soliciting that part may be reserved for their use. Chearfulness again appears on every countenance; and an universal faith prevails in the sovereign virtues of the re-

p.353

medy. The herbs now began to spring up above the ground; we of these made decoctions⁵; to which wormwood and camphire were added, that by their prevalent flavour, the medicines might appear of no mean efficacy. The stiff contracted limbs were anointed with wax melted in rape-seed, or lint-seed oil. The invention of new and untried physic is boasted; and amidst a defect of every necessary and useful medicine, a strange medley of drugs was compounded. The effect however of the delusion was really astonishing: for many were quickly and perfectly recovered. Such as had not moved their limbs

3 Countenance. the appearance of someone's face.

4 In the original, *Omne chaos morborum.*

for a month before, were seen walking the streets sound, upright, and in perfect health. They boasted of their cure by the Prince's remedy; the motion of their joints being restored by a simple friction with oil, Nature now of itself well performing its office, or at least with a small assistance from medicine. Many who declared they had been rendered worse by all former remedies which had been administered, recovered in a few days, to their inexpressible joy, and the no less general surprise, by the taking (almost by their having brought to them) what we affirmed to be their gracious Prince's cure.⁶

p.354

Soon after this their old calamity the plague broke out again. Not one in a hundred escaped of those who were seized with it. So that a victorious *Spanish* army, an eight months famine, the rage of the plague within, and the fury of the bombshells from without, depopulating and laying waste the city, the promiscuous funerals of parents and friends, the dismal apprehensions of a disheartened and reduced garrison, want of medicines and common necessaries, bad and unnatural food, having all conspired to the ruin of

p.355

this important place, it was surrendered by

capitulation in *June*.

As to the scurvy. This calamity proved most fatal to the *English* soldiers, as they very early began to feed on dogs flesh, were in want of their beloved tobacco, and lay in the most wet damp barracks. It was much less frequent among the *Waloons* and *Flemings*, they being more careful and delicate in their diet, and having much better quarters. Among the *French* it was seldom to be met with, owing entirely to their being stationed in the driest part of the town, and to their natural sprightly disposition, which kept them constantly employed in some motion or exercise, singing, and the like. I do not here touch upon the many different symptoms described by authors in this disease; those that occurred in this siege, I have faithfully related.

From which it will appear, that the scurvy is not a complication of many different diseases, but is itself a simple identical disease. It is extremely difficult, during the time of a long close siege, to preserve the citizens and soldiers from this cruel disaster. I am persuaded the best method would be to permit them the use of brandy or spirits during a cold moist season, and when wholesome food is wanting. Washing the mouth with brandy is excellent for preserving the gums and teeth.

5 Decoction. A liquid made by boiling something such as a plant in water

6 [Lind's comments on the Vander Mye report]

This curious relation would perhaps hardly gain credit, was it not in every respect consonant to the most accurate observations, and best attested descriptions of the disease. See Lord *Anson's* voyage, part 3. *Item*, Mr. *Ives's* journals, p. 94, &c. It is given us by an eyewitness, an author of great candour and veracity, who, as he informs us, wrote every day down the state of his patients; and seems more to be surprised with their unexpected recovery, than he possibly would have been, had he formerly been better acquainted with the nature of this surprising disease. These facts were then also notoriously known to many, at the time when he published his book, viz. the second year after they happened.

Might not the speedy recovery of the patients be partly owing to the decoction of the green herbs beginning to sprout up? Be that as it may. An important lesson in physic is here to be learned, viz. the wonderful and powerful influence of the passions of the mind upon the state and disorders of the body. This is too often overlooked in the cure of diseases; many of which are sometimes attempted by the sole mechanical operation of drugs, without calling in to assistance the strong powers of imagination, or the concurring influences of the soul. Hence it is, that the same remedy will not always produce the like effect even in the same person, when given by different hands; and that common cures often prove wonderfully successful in the hands of bold quacks, but do not answer the purpose in a timorous and distrustful practitioner.